

ACCEPTABILITY OF OFF-GRID RENEWABLE ENERGY AND VIABLE BUSINESS MODELS FOR RURAL ELECTRIFICATION IN NORTH-CENTRAL NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the acceptability of off-grid renewable energy systems and the viability of business models for rural electrification in North-Central Nigeria. A descriptive research design was adopted, covering selected states and relevant institutions. The study population comprised 1,150 respondents, from which a sample of 291 participants—including lecturers, entrepreneurs, ministry personnel, and community leaders—was selected. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and the Kruskal–Wallis H test at a 0.05 level of significance, with Dunn–Bonferroni post hoc analysis applied where necessary. Findings revealed a moderate to high level of acceptability of off-grid power solutions across all stakeholder groups, with community members showing slightly higher acceptance. The Kruskal–Wallis test indicated no statistically significant difference in perceptions of acceptability among respondents, suggesting a shared consensus. The study also found strong agreement on the viability of business models such as Pay-As-You-Go, mini-grids, Energy-as-a-Service, and public-private partnerships. However, a statistically significant difference was observed in perceptions of these models, with lecturers expressing stronger agreement than Ministry personnel. The study concludes that off-grid renewable energy systems are widely accepted and represent a viable solution for rural electrification. Based on the findings, it is recommended that stakeholders leverage the high level of community acceptance by actively involving local communities in the planning, implementation, and management of off-grid projects to enhance sustainability. Additionally, efforts should be made to strengthen alignment between policy actors and other stakeholders by addressing institutional concerns through improved regulatory clarity, stakeholder engagement, and capacity-building to increase confidence in the viability of off-grid business models.

INTRODUCTION

Access to reliable and affordable electricity is widely acknowledged as a critical driver of economic development, improved living standards, and poverty reduction. However, a significant proportion of the population in developing countries, particularly in rural and remote areas, still lacks access to electricity. In Nigeria, there is a persistent disparity between urban and rural electrification levels, with rural communities being disproportionately underserved (Aliyu et al., 2015). Reports indicate that a substantial segment of the rural population lacks stable electricity supply, thereby limiting economic opportunities and social development.

The inadequacy of electricity access in Nigeria is largely linked to the limitations of the centralized national grid. The grid is characterized by inefficiencies such as poor maintenance, overloading, and high transmission losses (Salihu et al., 2020). Furthermore, extending grid infrastructure to remote areas is often economically and technically impractical due to high capital costs and geographical challenges. Consequently, rural communities remain largely excluded from reliable electricity, while even urban areas experience frequent power outages (Audu & Adamu, 2022). These challenges highlight the need for alternative approaches to energy provision.

In response, the Federal Government established the Rural Electrification Agency (REA) to expand electricity access across the country. The agency aims to bridge the electrification gap and promote socio-economic development. Despite these efforts, progress has been limited, indicating persistent structural and policy-related challenges in the energy sector. Additionally, rapid population growth has further increased the demand for reliable and sustainable energy systems, making it imperative to explore innovative solutions (Samuel et al., 2022).

Off-grid electrification has emerged as a viable alternative to conventional grid extension, particularly in remote and underserved areas. Off-grid systems are decentralized energy solutions that operate independently of the national grid, allowing localized generation and distribution of electricity (Tania & Anisuzzaman, 2016). These systems offer several advantages, including reduced transmission losses, flexibility, and scalability to meet growing energy demands. They also support environmental sustainability by promoting the use of renewable energy sources and reducing reliance on fossil fuels.

Several off-grid technologies are suitable for rural electrification, depending on local resource availability. Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems are widely adopted due to their reliability and the abundance of solar resources in Nigeria (Sunday et al., 2023). Small hydropower systems are effective in areas with sufficient water resources, while wind energy systems have limited applicability in inland regions. Biomass gasification systems also provide an alternative by converting agricultural residues into energy, although sustainability considerations must be addressed. A key advantage of these technologies is their modular and scalable nature, which allows gradual expansion as energy demand increases (Salihu et al., 2020).

Despite their technical potential, the success of off-grid systems depends largely on community acceptance and participation. Acceptance is influenced by factors such as perceived socio-economic benefits, affordability, reliability, and cultural compatibility. Communities are more likely to adopt off-grid solutions when they experience improvements in living conditions, including better education, increased income-generating opportunities, and enhanced quality of life (Babalola et al., 2022). However, long-term acceptance requires consistent system performance and reliability. Technical performance is a crucial determinant of user satisfaction. Systems that frequently fail or require complex

maintenance often lead to dissatisfaction, particularly in rural areas where technical expertise is limited. Therefore, off-grid systems must be designed to be simple, reliable, and easy to maintain locally. Technologies that align with local technical capacities are more likely to achieve sustained adoption

Affordability is another key factor influencing adoption. While initial installation costs may be subsidized, ongoing maintenance and replacement costs can pose financial challenges for low-income households. Addressing this issue requires innovative financing mechanisms and sustainable business models. Integrating energy systems with local economic activities can further enhance financial viability by generating income that supports system operation and maintenance. Community engagement is essential for ensuring the success and sustainability of off-grid electrification projects. Involving community members in planning, design, and implementation fosters a sense of ownership and trust (Agoundemba et al., 2023). Participatory approaches also ensure that energy solutions are tailored to local needs and socio-cultural contexts, thereby improving their acceptance. In addition, awareness campaigns and training programs can help overcome skepticism and promote understanding of off-grid technologies

The broader economic and policy environment also plays a significant role in shaping the adoption of off-grid systems. Factors such as affordability, reliability, and social influence have been identified as key determinants of user acceptance (Bhattacharyya, 2018). Supportive government policies, including subsidies and incentives for renewable energy investments, are essential for promoting adoption. Conversely, weak regulatory frameworks and inadequate institutional support can hinder implementation

Aims and objective of the study

1. The acceptability of off-grid renewable energy power communities in North-central Nigeria.
2. The most viable business models for implementing off-grid electrification projects in rural communities of North-Central Nigeria

Research Questions

1. To what extent will off-grid renewable energy power be acceptable in rural communities in North-central Nigeria?
2. What are the most viable business models for implementing off-grid electrification projects in rural communities of North-Central Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁ There is no statistically significant difference between the mean responses of Ministry Personnel, Entrepreneurs, and Community Members on acceptable off-grid renewable energy power in rural communities.

Ho₂ There will be no significant differences among entrepreneurs in the renewable energy sector, and community leaders on the preferred business models for implementing off-grid electrification projects in rural communities of North-Central Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The research was conducted in North-Central Nigeria, specifically covering Benue, Kogi, Nasarawa, and Niger States, as well as the

Federal Ministry of Power in Abuja. The population of the study comprised 1,150 respondents, from which a sample size of 291 was determined using the Morgan table. The sample included engineering and technology lecturers specializing in electrical power systems, renewable energy entrepreneurs, personnel from the Ministry of Power and related agencies, and community leaders. Data were collected using a researcher-designed instrument titled Off-Grid Renewable Energy Power Supply Questionnaire (OGRPSQ), which contained 177 items.

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations. For hypothesis testing, the Kruskal–Wallis H test was employed at a 0.05 level of significance to determine differences among respondent groups. Where significant differences were identified, Dunn's post-hoc pairwise comparison test with Bonferroni correction was applied. Interpretation of responses was guided by the real limits of the Likert scale.

Result and discussion

Research Question one: To what extent will off-grid power solutions be acceptable in rural communities in North-central Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Perceptions on Community Acceptability of Off-Grid Power Solutions ($n_1 = 180$, $n_2 = 142$, $n_3 = 42$)

S/N	Statements	M ₁	SD ₁	M ₂	SD ₂	M ₃	SD ₃
1	Accept adoption of alternative electricity solutions	2.88	1.09	2.81	1.11	2.98	1.14
2	Support community-wide solar or hybrid systems	2.98	1.09	2.94	1.06	3.05	1.22
3	Trust organisations promoting renewable energy	3.25	0.96	3.22	0.93	3.18	1.01
4	Willing to participate in community-owned projects	3.33	2.44	3.19	0.99	3.03	1.03
5	Value involvement of community leaders	3.21	0.98	3.14	1.01	3.18	1.06
6	Willing to attend awareness programmes	3.02	1.06	3.13	1.06	2.88	1.20
7	Consider off-grid energy viable long-term	2.89	1.09	3.07	1.10	2.63	1.10
8	Alignment with cultural and religious values	3.03	1.06	3.16	1.11	2.90	1.10
9	Support discussing energy in community meetings	3.23	1.11	3.33	1.13	3.35	1.21
10	Encouraged by past energy projects	3.25	1.07	3.18	1.09	3.18	1.20

11	Community can operate and maintain systems	3.20	1.02	3.10	1.08	3.03	1.14
12	Trust in managing shared infrastructure	3.39	0.94	3.36	0.90	3.38	1.00
13	Willing to encourage others	3.68	0.84	3.19	1.03	3.33	1.12
14	Elders support clean energy	3.28	1.05	3.16	1.11	3.18	1.15
15	Support training initiatives	3.24	1.02	3.27	0.98	3.23	1.12
16	Support replacing petrol generators	3.14	0.99	3.04	1.00	3.30	0.91
17	Support youth training programmes	3.10	0.98	2.99	0.96	3.20	0.94
18	Cultural and religious alignment	3.18	0.95	3.15	1.01	3.03	0.86
19	Open to private sector partnerships	3.26	0.95	3.22	1.03	2.98	0.83
20	Accept decentralised community-managed systems	3.16	1.01	3.09	1.06	2.93	1.02
21	Confidence in sustaining off-grid systems	3.19	0.93	3.05	1.04	3.00 (0.85)	0.85
Overall Mean & SD		3.17	1.20	3.11	1.04	3.06	1.07

Key: n_1 = community, n_2 = entrepreneurs, n_3 = ministry, M_1 = mean of community, M_2 = mean of entrepreneurs, M_3 = mean of ministry, SD_1 = standard deviation of community, SD_2 = standard deviation of entrepreneurs, SD_3 = standard deviation of ministry of personnel

The results presented in Table 5 and Figure 5 indicate generally positive perceptions of community acceptability of off-grid power solutions across the three respondent groups. The overall mean scores, shown in the final row of Table 5, reveal that community members reported the highest level of agreement ($M = 3.17$, $SD = 1.20$), followed closely by entrepreneurs ($M = 3.11$, $SD = 1.04$) and Ministry personnel ($M = 3.06$, $SD = 1.07$). These mean values, all exceeding the scale midpoint of (lower limit = 2.61, upper limit = 3.40), suggest a moderate to high level of support for off-grid power projects, including willingness to participate in community-owned projects, support for training and awareness programmes, and confidence in the community's ability to sustain decentralised energy systems. The relatively comparable SD across the three groups indicate a similar spread of responses, implying shared perceptions among stakeholders despite differences in professional roles.

Research Question one: What are the most viable business models for implementing off-grid electrification projects in rural communities of North-Central Nigeria?

Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Perceptions of Viable Business Models for Off-Grid Electrification in Rural Communities ($n_1 = 87$; $n_2 = 142$, $n_3 = 42$)

S/N	Statements	M_1	SD_1	M_2	SD_2	M_3	SD_3
1	PAYG model is viable	4.14	0.81	4.22	0.81	3.95	0.39
2	EaaS improves affordability	4.20	0.83	4.22	1.01	4.08	0.53
3	Mini-grid model is sustainable	4.17	0.82	3.95	1.24	4.00	1.11
4	Community-owned models promote sustainability	4.14	0.89	4.18	0.95	3.68	1.21
5	Private sector involvement is essential	4.02	0.91	4.19	0.73	4.03	2.18
6	PPP model is effective	4.05	0.93	3.94	0.98	3.65	1.05
7	Subsidy-based models improve access	4.09	0.88	4.01	1.08	4.13	0.79
8	Donor-funded models are reliable initially	4.17	0.94	4.17	1.12	3.53	1.30
9	Flexible payment options increase adoption	4.13	0.99	4.25	3.66	3.68	1.27
10	Local entrepreneurship is critical	4.16	0.97	3.72	1.30	3.45	1.26
11	Government + private investment improves outcomes	4.76	0.87	4.17	0.96	4.13	0.85
12	Regular maintenance ensures sustainability	4.17	0.87	4.26	0.87	3.75	1.32
13	Financing options encourage adoption	4.21	0.94	4.08	1.12	4.45	0.75
14	Community-private partnerships improve performance	4.22	0.87	4.24	0.89	3.93	1.27
15	End-user involvement improves success	4.21	0.86	4.15	1.04	3.85	1.29
16	Transparent billing increases willingness to pay	4.25	0.70	4.09	0.99	4.58	0.50
17	Affordable tariffs enhance sustainability	4.71	0.83	4.29	0.70	4.13	0.33
18	Limited technical expertise constrains success	4.20	0.88	4.19	0.95	3.33	1.67

19	Income-generating energy use improves viability	4.18	0.83	4.32	0.76	4.68	0.73
20	Overall satisfaction with current business models	4.24	0.76	4.44	0.50	3.83	1.34
Overall Mean and SD		4.21	0.90	4.17	1.04	4.01	1.11

Key: n_1 = lecturers, n_2 = entrepreneurs, n_3 = ministry, M_1 = mean of lecturers, M_2 = mean of entrepreneurs, M_3 = mean of ministry, SD_1 = standard deviation of lecturers, SD_2 = standard deviation of entrepreneurs, SD_3 = standard deviation of ministry personnel.

The results presented in Table 7 shows a strong agreement among respondents regarding the viability of various business models for implementing off-grid electrification in rural communities. As shown in the overall mean row in Table 7, lecturers reported the highest level of agreement ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.90$), followed closely by entrepreneurs ($M = 4.17$, $SD = 1.04$) and Ministry personnel ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 1.11$). These mean scores, all well above the midpoint of the scale, suggest a broadly positive perception of existing and emerging off-grid business models. High ratings across key items indicate strong support for Pay-As-You-Go, mini-grid, Energy-as-a-Service, and community-owned models, particularly when combined with private sector participation, public-private partnerships, flexible payment mechanisms, and access to financing.

Hypothesis one

There is no statistically significant difference between the mean responses of Ministry Personel, Entrepreneurs, and Community Members on acceptable off-grid renewable energy power in rural communities.

Kruskal-Wallis Test Comparing Perceptions of Off-Grid Technologies Acceptability Across Respondent Groups

Group	n	Mean Rank	$\chi^2 (2)$	P.value	Effect Size (η^2_h)
Community	180	80.25	3.61	0.164	0.009
Ministry	42	85.33			
Entrepreneurs	142	91.69			
Total	364				

Note: η^2_h (eta-squared for Kruskal-Wallis) was calculated using $\eta^2_h = (H - k + 1)/(N - k)$, where $H = 3.612$, $k = 3$ groups, and $N = 364$.

The results indicated in Table 3 that there was no statistically significant difference between the groups, $\chi^2(2) = 3.61$, $p = 0.164$. Although entrepreneurs had a higher mean rank (91.69) compared to Ministry Personnel (85.33) and community members (80.25). These differences were not statistically significant. The calculated effect size was very small ($\eta^2_h = 0.009$), suggesting that respondent category accounted for less than 1% of the variance in perceived acceptability of off-grid technologies. Therefore, the null hypothesis was retained, indicating that perceptions of off-grid technologies acceptability do not significantly differ across respondent groups.

Hypothesis Two:

There will be no significant differences among entrepreneurs in the renewable energy sector, and community leaders on the preferred business models for implementing off-grid electrification projects in rural communities of North-Central Nigeria.

Table 2: Kruskal-Wallis Test Comparing Perceptions of Viable Business Models Across Respondent Groups

Group	n	Mean Rank	$\chi^2 (2)$	P.value	Effect Size (η^2_h)
Lecturers	85	146.10	9.974	0.007	0.030
Ministry	42	100.26			
Entrepreneurs	142	135.18			
Total	269				

Note: η^2_h (eta-squared for Kruskal-Wallis) was calculated using $\eta^2_h = (H - k + 1) / (N - k)$, where $H = 9.974$, $k = 3$ groups, and $N = 269$.

A Kruskal-Wallis H test was conducted to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in perceptions of viable business models for off-grid electrification among lecturers, Ministry personnel, and entrepreneurs. The results as shown in Table 2 revealed a statistically significant difference between groups, $\chi^2(2) = 9.97$, $p = 0.007$. Lecturers had the highest mean rank (146.10), followed by entrepreneurs (135.18), while Ministry personnel recorded the lowest mean rank (100.26). The effect size was small ($\eta^2_h = 0.030$), indicating that respondent category accounted for approximately 3% of the variance in perceptions of viable business models. Given the significant result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This suggests that perceptions of viable business models for off-grid electrification differ significantly across respondent groups.

Since the Kruskal-Wallis test was statistically significant, $\chi^2(2) = 9.97$, $p = 0.007$, a pairwise comparison were performed using the **Dunn procedure with Bonferroni correction** to control for Type I error across three comparisons (α adjusted = $0.05/3 = 0.017$) as presented in Table 4: **Post Hoc Pairwise Comparisons for Viable Business Model**

Comparison	Mean Rank Difference	Adjusted p-value	Interpretation
Lecturer vs Ministry	45.84	0.006	Significant
Lecturer vs Entrepreneurs	10.92	0.284	Not Significant
Entrepreneurs vs Ministry	34.92	0.021	Not Significant (after Bonferroni adjustment)

Bonferroni-adjusted significance level = 0.017.

Following a significant Kruskal–Wallis test, Dunn–Bonferroni post hoc analysis (adjusted $\alpha = 0.017$) revealed that **only lecturers and Ministry personnel differed significantly,**

with lecturers showing higher perceptions of viable business models ($p = 0.006$). No significant differences were found between lecturers and entrepreneurs or between entrepreneurs and Ministry personnel after adjustment. Overall, the observed group difference was mainly driven by the gap between lecturers and Ministry personnel, while entrepreneurs' views were not significantly different from either group.

Findings of the study

Respondents generally showed moderate to high acceptance of off-grid power solutions, with community members expressing slightly stronger support. All stakeholder groups demonstrated willingness to adopt decentralized systems, supported by confidence in community participation, training, and public–private partnerships.

on the viability of various business models, including Pay-As-You-Go, mini-grids, Energy-as-a-Service, and public–private partnerships. Flexible payment systems, affordability, and blended financing were identified as critical for sustainability, alongside collaboration between government and private sector actors.

Although a statistically significant difference existed in perceptions of business model viability, lecturers expressed stronger agreement than Ministry personnel. However, the small effect size indicates that the practical difference across groups is limited.

Findings further revealed broad consensus across stakeholders on the acceptability of off-grid solutions, as no significant differences were observed. This suggests that social acceptance is not a major barrier to implementation, aligning with existing studies that highlight positive attitudes toward decentralized energy systems. However, challenges such as affordability, technical capacity, and governance remain critical.

Finally, while overall support for off-grid business models is strong, institutional actors appear more cautious compared to academics. This may be due to concerns about policy, regulation, and implementation risks. The implication is that improving regulatory clarity, strengthening institutional capacity, and promoting collaboration between public and private sectors are essential for successful deployment.

Discussion of Findings

The study found moderate-to-high acceptability of off-grid electricity solutions across community members, entrepreneurs, and Ministry personnel. Community members expressed the strongest support, followed closely by entrepreneurs and Ministry personnel, suggesting broad stakeholder endorsement of decentralized electrification. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences in perceptions of acceptability across these groups, indicating a shared consensus. This finding aligns with diffusion of innovation theory, which posits that widespread perceived benefits and compatibility reduce subgroup resistance to new technologies. It also corroborates previous studies, such as Haliru and Ahmed (2022), who reported favorable attitudes toward solar home systems among rural households, and Joseph et al. (2019), who observed that rural users adopt electricity for productive and domestic purposes despite systemic constraints. These results suggest that social acceptability is not a primary barrier, although practical implementation must still address affordability, technical capacity, and governance to ensure successful deployment.

Regarding off-grid business models, respondents across all groups showed strong agreement on the viability of Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG), Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS), mini-grids, community-owned models, public–private partnerships (PPPs), and flexible payment mechanisms. However, significant differences emerged in perceptions between stakeholder groups: lecturers reported higher agreement with the feasibility of these models than

Ministry personnel, while entrepreneurs' views did not significantly differ from either group after Bonferroni adjustment. This suggests that institutional actors may be more cautious or skeptical about business model feasibility, potentially due to regulatory, fiscal, or operational concerns. These findings are consistent with Haliru and Ahmed (2022), who emphasized the importance of innovative pricing models to bridge affordability gaps, and Meyer et al. (2021), who highlighted the need for enabling policy frameworks to facilitate collaboration between private enterprises and public institutions.

Overall, the findings indicate broad support for off-grid solutions and their business models, but also highlight the importance of strengthening institutional confidence. Clear regulatory guidance, risk-sharing mechanisms, and capacity-building initiatives are critical to aligning policy actors with implementation stakeholders. Addressing these factors is essential to ensure that off-grid electrification initiatives are both socially accepted and operationally sustainable, thereby contributing to rural development and enhanced energy access in underserved communities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study found that off-grid electricity solutions are broadly accepted across key stakeholders, including community members, entrepreneurs, and Ministry personnel, with community members expressing the highest level of support. While lecturers reported slightly stronger confidence in the viability of off-grid business models than Ministry personnel, overall agreement existed regarding models such as Pay-As-You-Go, mini-grids, Energy-as-a-Service, and public-private partnerships. These findings indicate that social acceptance is not a major barrier to implementation. However, successful deployment requires addressing challenges related to affordability, technical capacity, governance, and institutional confidence, ensuring that off-grid systems are both socially and operationally sustainable.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. Policymakers should provide clear regulatory frameworks and supportive policies to reduce institutional skepticism and enhance confidence in business model viability. Flexible financing mechanisms, including Pay-As-You-Go and blended subsidy models, should be implemented to improve affordability for rural households. Technical training and participatory approaches should empower local communities to manage and maintain systems effectively, fostering ownership and sustainability. Additionally, fostering collaboration between government, private sector, and community stakeholders will help align policy, implementation, and operational objectives, ensuring the successful scaling of off-grid electrification initiatives.

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